

CRITICAL DEFECTS IN ADHESIVE TUBULAR JOINTS OF GRP PROCESS PIPES DETERMINED WITH ACOUSTIC EMISSION

Bjørn Melve, STATOIL Research Centre, Postuttak, N-7004 Trondheim
Bjarne Moursund, Norsk Hydro Research Centre, N-3901 Porsgrunn

ABSTRACT

A set of double muff tubular adhesive joint with different defects was made from a commercial 100 mm diameter glass fibre reinforced epoxy pipe. The defects simulated were: areas without bonding up to 85 % of the overlap area, humid adherents and misalignment of pipes in the muff. The pipes were pressurised in a stepwise manner up to 1.5 times the design pressure and the acoustic emission activity was recorded simultaneously. After the first loading, the pipes were unloaded and pressurised until failure. Acoustic emission did identify the only critical defect, which was the joint with 85 % of the area without bonding. Stress analyses also show that this defect is critical. An ordinary pressure test would not have identified this defect.

Keywords: Glass fibres, Epoxy, Adhesive, tubular joints, GRP-Pipes, Acoustic emission, Critical defects.

1. BACKGROUND

Low-pressure glass fibre reinforced polymer (GRP) - pipes are being used to an increasing extent on the offshore installations in the North Sea. On existing platforms glass fibre reinforced piping is replacing steel pipes where corrosion is a problem. On new platforms an increasing use is taking place because the engineering companies are being more used to the design and handling of GRP pipes. The pipes are being used to transport different sorts of fluids, mainly water-based media such as sea water (hot and cold) for cooling or fire systems. The media transported in the pipes are not dangerous to humans, and the pressure is usually below 2.5 MPa (25 bar). A minor leakage will not be hazardous, but a total failure of cooling water systems can lead to a stop in the production and an economical loss. Because of the excellent corrosion properties of GRP pipes can be good candidate for the transport of hydrocarbons (raw oil, natural gas) with quantities of CO₂ and H₂S. GRP pipes have been used as flow lines for oil onshore in USA for many years /1/, but the GRP pipes have not been used for transport of hydrocarbons on the Norwegian sector in the North sea. In such flow lines the pressures would be 5-10 times higher than the pressures in the already installed GRP-pipes. From a security point of view it is essential to have methods for evaluating the condition of the pipes transporting, otherwise they cannot be used in this critical application. In this work acoustic emission

have been used to test defects introduced into the adhesive joints and to identify the critical ones. Acoustic emission is established as a method for controlling GRP-pipes [2-4], and the method can directly give an answer to whether the condition of the tested system is acceptable or not. In contrast to other methods, acoustic emission can differentiate between critical and non-critical defects. The aim of the present work is to couple the acoustic emission and the size of critical defects. The stress analysis part is now being extended in other projects, and only the first results are presented here. Low pressure pipes up to 300 mm diameter are connected with adhesive joints through bell and spigot types of joints or through muff joints. Previous studies [5] have shown that most of the faults arise in the adhesive joints. Possible defects in these types of joints are:

- Lack of adhesive in parts of the joint
- Interface cracks between adhesive and adherents
- Under cured adhesive
- Pores and cracks in the adhesive
- Misalignment of adherents
- Wet surfaces
- Lacking surface treatment (degreasing, sanding)

Lack of adhesive in smaller or larger parts is a very probable defect and most of the work was concentrated on this type of defect.

1.1 Stress distribution in tubular joints

The first requirement for determining the criticality of defects in the adhesive joints is to have detailed knowledge of the distribution of stresses and strains. The stress state for a suspended pipe system will be internal pressure with full axial load from the pressure. In addition there might be some influence of bending between the pipe supports and local bending effects in bends and tee-joints. Here we consider only the double muff joint (tubular single lap joint). The joint will experience both axial loading and hoop loading. The critical stresses are the radial stresses opening the adhesive joint and the shear stress along the joint. Radial stresses will arise because the tendency to bending of the adherents in the overlap joint. The average shear stress τ_{rz} in the adhesive joint from an internal pressure P will be:

$$\tau_{rz} = F/A = P \pi (D_i/2)^2 / \pi D_a L \approx P D_i / 4L \quad (1)$$

where:

P = pressure

F = The tensile force because of biaxial loading from internal pressure

A = area of adhesive joint = $\pi D L$

D = Diameter of pipe, D_i internal diameter, D_a diameter to the adhesive layer.

This is the usual method of calculating the strength of tubular adhesive joints and is the basis for the calculation of the overlap lengths of joints in the different pipe classes. The overlap length is then adjusted to give a low enough shear stress to coincide with the recommended design shear strength of the adhesive. For a commercial 100 mm GRP pipe joined with a muff joint with an overlap of 40 mm and with a pressure of 2 MPa (≈ 20 bar) the average stress will be 1.25 MPa. The true stress distribution in a tubular adhesive joint between elastic adherents is different from this and will be high at the ends of the joint.

Lubkin and Reissner /6/ have analysed the stresses in tubular lap joints with isotropic materials and equal thickness of the adherents under a tensile axial load. Their values are cited in form of tables but are derived from a closed form theory. The results show that the adhesive shear stress and the normal radial stress are a maximum at the end of the adhesive layer. Because of the free surface at the end of the adhesive layer the shear stress must be zero here. They assumed that the tensile and shear stresses in the adherents could be neglected as long as the condition (2) is satisfied:

$$\beta = \frac{\eta E}{E_a t} \equiv \frac{\eta G}{G_a t} \geq 10 \quad (2)$$

where E and G are the Young's and shear moduli of the adherend, E_a and G_a are the Young's and shear moduli of the adhesive, t = thickness of adherend, η - thickness of the adhesive layer. For a composite pipe the modulus to be used would be the axial modulus E_{ZZ} of the pipe and muff joints. The hoop values will not enter into equation. The shear modulus would be the value G_{TZ} . An additional requirement was that thin shell theory could be applied, i.e. that the factor R is less than 0.10:

$$R = \frac{t}{2a} \leq 0.10 \quad (3)$$

For the composite pipes considered here the modulus of the adherents in the axial direction is 20 % or less of the similar modulus of aluminium. Therefore the condition (2) is seldom met. The second condition is fulfilled for the composite pipes in question. According to Adams and Peppiat /7/ the β -factor could be reduced to 3 and still the stresses in the adhesive will be an order of magnitude larger than in the adherents. This is not sufficient for the pipes in question. The tensile loadings of adhesive joints in composites have been the subject of papers where connections of struts and tubulars have been analysed /8/. The creep behaviour of the adhesive is shown to reduce the maximum shear and normal stresses in the steel tubular joint /9/. The creep behaviour of the adherents is not considered. Composite tubulars have also been studied in torsion and bending /10-11/ and the results are presented as the governing differential equations for the different loading conditions. The shear stress distribution due to tensile loading for different geometries including tubes can be calculated by the program THAMM /12/.

Because of the complexity of the problem for a standard pipe with non similar materials and thicknesses in the muffs and straight pipes the best way for an engineer to get the stress distribution is to use finite element modelling (FEM). The case of internal pressure in composite carbon-epoxy pipes has been studied with FEM-analysis by Habib et. al. /13/. They show that the stress distributions for the shear stress with internal pressure are quite similar to the distribution for a pure tensile load. However the radial stress (opening stress) is very much influenced by the internal pressure because of local bending.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Specimens

A set of 100 mm (4"), 2.0 MPa (20 bar) nominal pressure, commercially available epoxy pipe system was joined with double muff joints according to the instructions given in the installation manual. The muff and the shaved pipe ends were degreased, sanded and cleaned before the epoxy adhesive was applied. The joints were then cured with heating blankets for 1 hour at blanket temperature of 130 °C. The dimensions of the joint is given in figure 1. The diameter of the shaved part was 105.8 mm

compared to 106.4 mm of the pipe itself. The shaved length was 44 mm i.e. 3-4 mm longer than the overlap from the double muff. The approximate material properties of the pipe and adhesive are presented in table 1. The pipes had an 0.5 mm resin rich inner liner with a C-glass reinforcement. In the strength layer the glass fibres are E-glass and the matrix is a Shell Epikote 828 epoxy with an aromatic amine hardener. The volume fraction of glass fibres in the strength layer is $52 \pm 7\%$. The hardener of the adhesive hardener was an amine type. The properties of the adhesive are shown in table 2.

Table 1: Mechanical properties of the glass fibre reinforced pipes.

Winding angle ($^{\circ}$)	Axial modulus (MPa)	Axial strength (MPa)	Hoop modulus (MPa)	Hoop strength (MPa)	Poisson's ratio axial force hoop contr	Poisson's ratio hoop force axial contr	Volume fraction (%)
55	12000	75	20500	210	0.38	0.65	52 ± 7

Table 2: Measured properties of the epoxy adhesive.

Tensile strength (tensile test) (MPa)	Young's modulus (tensile test) (MPa)	Poisson's ratio (tensile test)	Shear strength (double lap shear test) (MPa)
28	850	0.35	22

Figure 1. The double muff joint of the glass fibre epoxy pipe used in the experiments.

The joints were conical (muff - female) / cylindrical (pipe - male) which give the highest thickness of the adhesive where the pipe leaves the muff. The following defects were introduced in the adhesive joint and are shown in figure 2:

- 14 mm tubular defect from the pipe end (35 % of the overlap),
- 14 mm tubular defect in the middle (35 % of the overlap),
- Humid adherents before application of adhesive,
- Large tubular defect (85 % of the overlap)
- A 25 mm semicircular defect from the pipe end,
- An axial misalignment of 2°

The defects were made by placing a thin PTFE film on the pipe end before joining. The PTFE-film would then ensure a lack of bonding.

Figure 2. The different defects in the pipe specimens introduced before pressure testing.

2.2 Test set-up

The pipes were supplied with metallic end fittings and filled with water. The pressure was then applied through the end fittings that gave the full biaxial loading from internal pressure. The metallic end fittings were isolated from the pipe with thin rubber sheets in order to avoid extra noise coming from the end fittings during pressurisation. The pressure was applied in steps: 1.5, 2.25, 2.5 and 3.0 MPa with a load hold period of 6 minutes at each level. 3.0 MPa corresponds to 1.5 times the nominal pressure of 2.0 MPa (20 bar). After this test the pipes were tested directly to failure or leakage.

2.3 Acoustic emission

Figure 3. The experimental set-up for pressure testing with the PAC acoustic emission system.

Acoustic emission (AE) was monitored with one integrated PAC R15I sensor from Physical Acoustic Corporation (PAC) on top of the double muff. The sounds were recorded with a PAC ATLAS 7016 acoustic emission equipment. The threshold level for recording the sounds was 45 dB. The AE-signals were recorded in three stages: a) during loading, b) first 2 minutes at load hold and c) last 4 minutes at load hold.

2.4 FEM-analysis

A model of the tubular joint was made with the program ANSYS /13/. The model can be simplified to an axisymmetric model of the joint. The model consisted of 480 axisymmetric elements where the pipe walls are modelled with orthotropic material properties. The model is shown in figure 4. The material properties in tables 1 and 2 were used for the modelling.

Figure 4. The mesh of the FEM-model of the 100 mm adhesive muff coupling.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Acoustic emission testing

All the pipes held the test pressure of 3.0 MPa. Figure 5 show the rate of acoustic emission events during the first two minutes of load hold versus pressure. The large defect is clearly the most active at the lowest pressures. The pipe with the semicircular edge defect also show a large activity in this figure. The sum of the acoustic emission counts and events are plotted in figure 6. The large defect is also the most active here. In the events plot 6a) the semicircular defect is still active, but when the counts (= number of threshold crossings) are plotted in 6 b) this defect is not so active. The semicircular defect is positioned in the area with the highest shear and radial stresses. It is therefore reasonable that this defect is more active than the ring defect in the same area. In an ordinary hydrotest of a pipe system, the large defect would not have been detected since there was no leakage at the test pressure. But acoustic emission could clearly distinguish this defect from the other defects.

Events during 2 mins load hold

Figure 5. The events recorded during the first two minutes of load hold for the glass fibre epoxy pipes with double muff joints and defects in the bondline.

a)

Events during 6 minutes load hold

b)

Figure 6. The sum of the acoustic emission, a) events and b) counts at the 6 minutes load hold period for the sequential pressure testing of the glass fibre epoxy pipes with double muffs with different defects.

After the acoustic emission test, the specimens were tested until failure. The specimen with the large defect failed at 4.4 MPa that is twice the nominal pressure. The other specimens were stronger. The different failure pressures are shown in figure 7. Because of the rubber sheets between the pipes and the metallic end couplings the leakage was in the couplings instead of the muff joint. The maximum pressures are therefore not always indicating the strength of the joint. Since the data are limited it is difficult to draw a firm conclusion with respect to failure pressures for the different defects. The pipe systems are designed with a safety factor of 3. The pipe with muff would not leak before the pressure reach at least 6 MPa. We can estimate that all these pipes would have survived at least this pressure if the end couplings had not started to leak.

Figure 7. Maximum pressure for the different defects shown in figure 1. Only the filled columns showed real failure in the joint, the others had failure (sliding) in the end fittings.

3.2 Criticality of defects

From the acoustic emission testing and the final pressure testing only the joint with the very large defect was really critical. The misalignment and the humid adherents did not influence on the results very much. The humidity can give e The small tubular defects (35 % of bondline) at the pipe end and in the middle does not appear to be critical for short term loading. If the same effect is active in for long term loadings this will confirm the non-criticality of these defects. Creep and fatigue loading can give negative effects that do not show in a short term test. The testing is done at room temperature

Figure 8 shows the deformation patterns from biaxial loading (internal pressure) and uniaxial tension from the FEM-model. The effect of the internal pressure is to introduce bending in the area where the pipe leaves the joint because of the stiff muff.

Figure 8. The deformation pattern of the FEM-model of the 100 mm tubular adhesive joint from biaxial loading from internal pressure (biaxial) and for uniaxial tension.

In figure 9 are shown the shear stress distributions calculated with THAMM /12/ for a tensile loading equivalent to 2 MPa pressure. The different overlap lengths show that the stress goes down to zero in the middle for the perfect and the one with the small defect. For the largest defect, the stress in the middle of the joint is rather high and is therefore more likely to fail in a test. The shear stress distributions for the joint confirms the observations from the acoustic emission testing. The specimen with the large defect failed at lower pressure than the others. The semicircular defect is positioned in the area with the highest shear stress and it therefore very possible that it will give some acoustic noises. The pipes with 35 % reduction of the bonded area would behave very much like the perfect joint. This is also confirmed with the pressure testing and acoustic emission testing.

At a pressure of 4.4 MPa where the large defect failed the maximum elastic shear stress would be around 24 MPa at the edges that is higher than the measured shear strength of the adhesive. This would lead to some kind of failure at the edges as was observed in the real test. The stress in the middle of the adhesive joint would be around 8 MPa, which is a significant stress with respect to the failure strength of the adhesive. In a long term loading at 2 MPa, the stress in the middle of the joint would lead to creep and a possible failure.

Figure 9. Adhesive shear stress distribution in the 40.5 mm tubular overlap joint in a 100 mm glass fibre epoxy pipe calculated with the program (THAMM) /11/. The overlap length is reduced in order to simulate a lack of bonding.

5. CONCLUSIONS

For these short-term loadings the standard tubular adhesive joint is over-designed with a large failure tolerance. From the shear stress distributions in the tubular joint it is clear that only the large defect is structurally significant. Only the large defect gave significant acoustic emission.

Acoustic emission could distinguish between critical and non-critical defects in a the short term loading. This is a large advantage with acoustic emission compared to other NDT-methods. With ultrasound and X-ray the defects could have been found, but the criticality would not be known. The ordinary design for tubular adhesive joints are very failure tolerant and defects up to 30 % of the area are not critical of the short term loading.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the work of Per Renolen for testing of adhesives and preparation of pipes, Reidar Andersen and T. Schjelderup for FEM-calculations. The work was sponsored by Nordic Industrial Foundation through contract 90015. Thanks to Sverre Schlytter-Henrichsen and Wavin Repox BV. for providing the pipes.

References

1. Chiu, A.S. and Franco, R.J., *FRP Line pipe for Oil and Gas Production*, Materials Performance, August, 1989, pp 64-69.
2. T. Fowler, T., *New Directions In Testing*, Third Int. Int. Symposium on AE from Composites, Paris, July 1989, American Society for Non-Destructive testing

3. Drodge M., *Recommended Practice for Acoustic Emission Testing of Fiberglass Reinforced Piping Systems*, CARP-Committee, 1st Int. Symposium on Acoustic Emission From Reinforced Composites, July 19-21, 1983
4. *Standard Practice for Acoustic Emission Examination of Reinforced Thermosetting Resin Pipe (RTRP)*, ASTM E1118-86, American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia
5. Fredriksen, A., Taberner, D, Ramstad, J.E., Steensland, O., Funnemark, E., *Reliability of GRP Sea water Piping Systems*, Veritec report no. 90-3520, Oslo, 1990
6. Lubkin, J. L., and Reissner, E. *Stress Distribution and Design Data for Adhesive Lap Joints Between Circular Tubes*, Trans. ASME, Vol. 78, 1956, pp. 1213-1221
7. Adams, R.D., Peppiat, N.A., *Stress Analysis of Adhesive Bonded Tubular Lap Joints*, J. Adhesion, 1977, Vol. 9., pp. 1-18
8. Pickett, A.K. and Holloway, L. *The Analysis of Adhesive Stresses in Bonded Lap Joints in FRP Structures*, Composite Structures vol., 3, 1985, 55-79
9. Alwar and Nagaraja, *Viscoelastic Analysis of an Adhesive Tubular Joint*, J. Adhesion, Vol. 8, pp. 79-92. 1976
10. Updike, D.P. and Yuceoglu, U., *Tubular Lap Joints in Composite Cylindrical Shells under External Bending and Shear*, Fourth Int. Conference on Composite Materials, ICCM-IV, Tokyo, 1982, pp. 297-304
11. Yuceoglu, U. and Updike, D.P., *Stresses in Two-Layer Bonded Orthotropic Cylindrical Shells*, In Emerging technologies in Aerospace structures, Design, Structural Dynamics and Materials, ASME-publication, 1980, pp. 53-65
12. Groth, H., *THAMM, user guide, Dimensionering og design*, in Limhåndbog, Dansk Teknologisk Institut, July 1991, ISBN 87-7754-037-9, pp. 96-120
13. Habib, M., Aivazzadeh and Verchery, G., *Analysis of Adhesively Bonded Composite Tubes under Different Loading Condition using Axisymmetric Interface Finite Elements*, Conf. on. Advances in Adhesively Bonded Joints, Chicago, IL, 1988, American Society for Mechanical Engineers, Materials Division (publ). V6, pp. 33-41 (AMEMD9)
14. Schjelderup, T. *FEM-analyse av limt rørskjøt (FEM-analysis of an Adhesively bonded tubular joint)*, SINTEF-report STF20 F92143, Trondheim, 1992